

STRATEGIC DEVELOPEMENT OF SAWENTAR VILLAGE TOURISM IN KANIGORO DISTRICTS, BLITAR REGENCY

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Abstract: Blitar Regency, East Java Province, Indonesia, is one of the regions that continues to develop tourism. One type of tourist attraction that continues to be developed in Blitar Regency is a tourist village. In 2020 it was registered that there were 24 Tourism Villages in Blitar Regency. In 2021, there are around 11 tourist villages that will be appointed as tourist villages under the supervision of the Tourism, Culture, Youth and Sports (DISPARBUDPORA) Blitar Regency. One of the 11 tourist villages, which has been designated as a tourist village by the DISPARBUDPORA of Blitar Regency in February 2021, is the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village, which is located in Kanigoro District, Blitar Regency. The tourism development strategy itself is important to develop and advance a tourist destination, including a tourist village, let alone a new tourism village (pilot). So in this study, we discuss the development strategy in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village using the Tourism Area Life Cycle (TALC) theoretical basis and the concept of Tourism, Tourism Attraction Components, Tourism Villages, Tourism Development and Tourism Development Strategies, CBT, CBT Development Strategies, Marketing, and the Concept of Tour Packages. The data collection techniques for this research were observation, interviews with purposive sampling, documentation, and SWOT analysis techniques.

This study focuses on the analysis of existing tourism activities in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village and strategies that can be taken to develop and advance tourism activities in the village. From this research, it can be concluded that the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village is a tourism village that is in the exploration stage and has shown a transition to the involvement stage. Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village has both driving and inhibiting factors in tourism activities, both in terms of attractions, accessibility, amenities, and enthusiasm. In its development, strategies that can be carried out are strategies for strengthening human resources, strategies for making tour packages, and marketing strategies.

Keywords: Tourist Village, Strategic Development, Strategic Development of Tourist Village, Community Based Tourism.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourism is one of the fields that is the largest contributor to foreign exchange in Indonesia. In 2015, citing the Indonesian Information Portal, it was stated that tourism contributed USD12.23 billion of foreign exchange or equivalent to Rp.171.22 trillion (indonesia.go.id, 2021). With this amount, tourism becomes the fourth largest foreign exchange earner after gas and natural oil, coal, and palm oil. The tourism sector also continues to grow every year. Although it experienced

an insignificant decline in 2016, the tourism sector has proven that the tourism sector can continue to advance and can provide foreign exchange and absorb labor which is increasing every year.

The existence of the Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic that has shaken the whole world has become a big enough obstacle for the tourism sector throughout the world, including Indonesia. The pandemic period does not allow free mobility, especially in the form of tourism visits. Since February 2020, the number of foreign tourists entering Indonesia has decreased very significantly, where in April 2020, there were only 158,000 tourists. In total, throughout 2020, the number of foreign tourists who entered Indonesia was only around 4.052 million people (kemenparekraf.go.id, 2021). It can be seen in table 1.2 Table 1.2 Number of Foreign Tourist Visits in 2017 Until 2021 where the number of tourist visits continued to increase from 2017 to 2019, then experienced a very drastic decline in 2020 and 2021.

This research is located in Blitar Regency. Blitar Regency is a regency in East Java Province, Indonesia. The district government center is in Kanigoro District after previously being in the same area as the city of Blitar. Blitar Regency is located on the coast of the Indonesian Ocean with the northern border with Kediri Regency, East with Malang Regency, South side with Indonesian Ocean and West side with Tulungagung Regency. In the middle of Blitar Regency itself, Blitar Regency is bordered by Blitar City. Blitar Regency has an area of 1,588.79 Km² or 158,879 Ha, with the largest sub-district area being Wonotirto District, with an area of 164.54 Km². While the smallest sub-district is Sanankulon District, which is 33.33 Km². Administratively, Blitar Regency consists of 22 (twenty-two) sub-districts and 248 villages/kelurahan. It was recorded that in 2020, the population of Blitar district was 1,223,745 people with a density of 770 people/km². Blitar Regency itself is one of the regions that participates in maximizing the tourism sector as one of the community's economic enhancers. Quoting from the Jawa Post, since 2019, based on data from the Blitar Regency Tourism, Culture, Youth and Sports Office (DISPARBUDPORA), the number of locations that have become tourist destinations in Blitar Regency has been around 35 villages. If developed to the maximum, the thirty-five destinations in 35 villages are very possible to develop and can become a mainstay tourist spot for Blitar Regency (radartulungagung.jawapos.com, 2019).

Data from the Tourism, Culture, Youth and Sports Office of Blitar Regency, hereinafter referred to as DISPARBUDPORA Blitar Regency, shows that in 2020, there are around 24 Tourism Villages in Blitar Regency, of which the twenty-four existing tourist villages are under the assistance of DISPARBUDPORA Blitar Regency with potential or different tourism advantages.

Assistance by DISPARBUDPORA Blitar Regency is carried out both for tourist villages and prospective tourism villages in Blitar Regency. Launching the East Java Times, in 2021, the Head of the Destination and Business Development Division of Blitar DISPARBUDPORA, Arinal Huda, said there were 11 tourist villages that would be designated as new tourist villages in Blitar Regency (jatimtimes.com, 2021). According to Blitar Regent Regulation Number 4 of 2017 concerning Guidelines for Establishing and Organizing Tourism Villages, a Tourism Village is an area whose supporters have activities in the social and economic fields in the form of tourism business development based on the potential for artificial and natural attractions, including cultural heritage and social structure. local community life, cultural values, traditional arts and crafts and traditional culinary as well as accommodation facilities. In its development, a good tourism village is a community-based tourism village. Community-based tourism is tourism where the community or local residents play an important and major role in decision making, where tourism affects and benefits their lives and environment (Prasiasa, 2013). One of the tourist villages of the 11 tourist villages mentioned by Mr. Arinal Huda as Head of the Destination and Business Development Division of DISPARBUDPORA Blitar is Sawentar Village, which has now been inaugurated and is in the development stage. In its development, Sawentar Village certainly cannot be separated from the realm of DISPARBUDPORA assistance in Blitar Regency.

When talking about Sawentar Village itself, tourism activities have started in Sawentar Village since the 2016s with the main attraction being Sawentar Temple. It can be seen from Table 1.3 Livelihoods of the Sawentar Tourism Village Community, although the livelihoods of local communities on average are farmers with a percentage of 45.8% (forty five point eight percent) and livestock farmers with a percentage of 30.4% (thirty point four percent), but based on the results of a preliminary interview with Mr. Nurfi as the Manager of the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village, he mentioned how since becoming the top four in the Gotong Royong Village competition in East Java Province in 2018, local communities in Sawentar Village began to have a desire to advance the village, one of which was One is through tourism activities.

In 2018, the main tourism activities carried out by local communities were still centered on one attraction, namely Sawentar Temple. Candi Sawentar is a temple with Singasari style, where this temple has parts of the foot-body-roof of the temple with a temple room that can be entered from one door which is usually on the west side. Indeed, there are two Sawentar Temples, namely Sawentar I Temple and Sawentar II Temple. Sawentar I Temple is a temple that has been widely known and is an icon of Sawentar Village tourism since 2016, while Sawentar II Temple itself is not widely known by tourists. In addition, the temple or Sawentar II site still needs restoration and more organized maintenance.

In addition to having cultural heritage which has become a tourist icon since 2016, Sawentar Village is also considered to have culture and art that can be developed and used as a tourist attraction. So in February 2021, Sawentar Village was inaugurated as a tourist village, more precisely a Cultural Tourism Village. As the name implies, Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village has the main tourism products based on culture, whether in the form of cultural education, arts, and traditional sports. With its cultural potential, Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village has a great opportunity to become one of the leading tourist villages in Blitar Regency.

Even so, in its development, the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village still has many shortcomings, as the local people there are still so unfamiliar with tourism activities. From a preliminary interview with the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village Manager, Mr. Nurfi, it is known that the manager and POKDARWIS have prepared a tour package since early 2021, but until now, the manager has stated that the tour package that has been prepared has not been able to run properly. Tourists tend to come to see the attractions of Sawentar Temple only, have not bought the tour packages offered and have been promoted. These two things become the urgency of making research in this Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village. From these two things, the author takes the title "Development Strategy of Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village in Kanigoro District, Blitar Regency". In writing this research, the author analyzes the driving and inhibiting factors of tourism activities in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village, and develops appropriate strategies to be able to advance tourism activities in the village, based on these factors. The driving factor is a factor in the form of strength and opportunity (strength and opportunity), while the inhibiting factor is a factor in the form of weakness and threat (weakness and threat). In this study, the driving and inhibiting factors were examined through four instruments, namely 4 components of tourist attraction in Sawentar Tourism Village. The 4 components consist of attraction, accessibility, amenity and ancillary services according to Cooper et al (1995). The author hopes, with this research, the author is able to help Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village in developing ongoing tourism activities.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

The data analysis technique used in this research is descriptive qualitative analysis. According to Moleong (2007:3) states that qualitative analysis is a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of words or words from people and observed behavior.

The SWOT analysis technique according to Istiqomah (2017), is part of the assessment of the results of the identification of the situation, in order to determine a condition that is categorized as strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. This analysis is part of planning, this is done in the planning process to find out current conditions and future plans that can have an impact on the process.

The matrix will be divided into two parts, namely internal factors and external factors. Included in the internal category are strengths and weaknesses, then those included in the external category are opportunities and threats (opportunity and threat). Each of these factors will then be entered into an IFAS (Internal Factor Analysis Summary) table and an EFAS (External Factor Analysis Summary) table by giving a weight (0.00-1.00) and a rating (1-4) on the SWOT factors. that have been identified. Each weight scale starts from 0.00 (not important) to 1.00 (most important) while the rating scale starts from 1 (poor) to 4 (outstanding) based on the influence of these factors on tourism activities in Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village. The weights and ratings are then multiplied and then added up to get the total score from the IFAS and EFAS tables. The process of assigning weights and rating tables to IFAS and EFAS is based on the interview and observation process that has been carried out by researchers.

The results from the IFAS and EFAS tables will then be converted into an Internal-External matrix. According to Rangkuti (Rangkuti, 2015), the Internal - External matrix aims to sharpen the analysis and see the company's position and see the direction of further developments. The IE matrix is based on two key dimensions: the total IE weight score on the X axis and the total EFE weight score on the Y axis. The total weight score obtained then results in an array of IE Matrix.

Figures 1: IE Matrix

The IE matrix has 3 (three) different strategic implications, namely:

1. The total value on axes I, II, or IV is described as growth and build. So the appropriate strategy is an intensive strategy such as market penetration, market development, and product development.
2. The total value on the axis III, V or VII can use a strategy that intends to maintain and maintain (hold and maintain). Such as market penetration and product development strategies.
3. The total value on axes VI, VIII or IX can use a harvest or divestiture strategy (harvest or divestiture).

From these two categories, strategies will be produced. After knowing which axis is the total value of the IFAS and IFAS matrices, then a SWOT analysis matrix can be made.

III. RESULT

Tourism Activity at Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village

Tourism activities have started in Sawentar Village since 2016 with the main attraction (and also an icon) in the form of historical and cultural heritage, Sawentar Temple (image of Sawentar Temple can be seen in the attachment). In 2020, Sawentar Village began to pioneer tourism activities as a Cultural Tourism Village, where in this same year, the village began to design tour packages that can be offered and sold to tourists. Before being able to pioneer as an embryo tourism village (pilot), unfortunately the world was hit by the Corona Virus-19 pandemic, Indonesia was no exception, especially East Java, Blitar. The existence of a pandemic in the end forced Sawentar Village to postpone the launch of tour packages that had already begun to be designed. The Corona Virus-19 which has made the government limit mobility and especially tourism activities has made tourism activities in Sawentar Village as a tourist village unable to be carried out, however, the Department of Tourism, Culture, Youth and Sports (DISPARBUDPORA) of Blitar Regency, as a companion partner from Sawentar Village, continue to guide Sawentar Village in planning tourism activities that can be carried out in Sawentar Village, with the hope that when the pandemic ends, Sawentar Village can immediately sell tour packages that have been designed in such a way. Sawentar Tourism Village itself is a cultural-based tourism village, where the main attractions offered are of course various types of cultural-based activities.

On Tuesday, February 16, 2021, even though it is still in the shadow of a pandemic, to support Sawentar Village tourism activities later, the Blitar Regency DISPARBUDPORA issued a Decree on the Determination of a Tourism Village to Sawentar Village. Tourism packages have begun to be developed again by the village, which were designed together with local communities who are members of POKDARWIS. April 2021, tour packages made by local communities have been formed and have begun to be marketed, but due to the ongoing pandemic, these packages do not yet have enthusiasts. In the middle of 2021, when community mobility has started to loosen and tourism activities have started to be active again because the vaccine has been circulated, tourism activities that occurred in Sawentar Village can resume running, but tourists who come still visit Sawentar Temple, no one has bought a tour package. offered by the Sawentar Cultural

Tourism Village. there are four different tour packages on offer, starting at Rp. 35.000, - for a fairly short tourist activities up to the price of Rp. 110,000, - for tour packages that offer more complete and varied activities.

Tour packages offer various types of culture-based activities such as traditional sports, cultural education, arts, and historical tours. There are various kinds of traditional sports offered, namely traditional games or sports that are still sustainable and played by the local community, especially children in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village such as gobak sodor and mushrooms. The education offered starts from batik education, Organizing, to education in making bricks. Meanwhile, the arts offered are Jaranan, Tiban, and other arts that are still sustainable and still have art groups or associations in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village. Prospective tourists or tourists are not only invited to just see or observe, but also get directly involved in the activities that exist in the tour packages offered.

although this tour package is not yet in demand by tourists, homestays managed by local communities have been and are still running. Until now, Sawentar Village already has approximately 10 ten homestays that can accommodate tourists, where this homestay is a resident's house that offers a living room, bedroom, bathroom, drink, and meal once a day for tourists. The homestay owner usually provides food for the tourists who stay. The homestay owner also has a briefing on hospitality and homestay standardization provided by the DISPARBUDPORA Blitar Regency. Supporting facilities for tourism activities are also owned, although not yet complete, such as public toilets, prayer rooms, to various types of stalls and a market near Sawentar Temple. The local community is also very enthusiastic in responding to tourism activities in Sawentar Village. In addition, the Village Government and BUMDES also want to work well together in supporting tourism activities in Sawentar Village.

Since the inauguration of Sawentar Village as a tourist village through a decree given by DISPARBUDPORA Blitar Regency, the village government has provided input to the village on what tourism activities might be developed in Sawentar Village. One thing that is still lacking in tourism activities in Sawentar Village is the lack of local community competence in knowledge in the tourism sector.

Entering the end of 2021 when tourism activities can run more loosely while still prioritizing health protocols. In an interview with the Sawentar Tourism Village Manager, it was found that the activities in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village had not developed much. Until now, the only tourist attraction that is visited is Sawentar Temple. Other tourism activities that are still ongoing are batik education by local communities, and bird competitions which are held regularly, which are participated by local communities and communities around Sawentar Village. This competition event is usually held near Sawentar Temple and the market which is also managed by the local community. As for the unified tour package offered by the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village, it has not been able to run and has not received interest from tourists.

Looking at the current condition of the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village, studied through the Tourism Area Life Cycle (TALC) theory, which is a tourism life cycle theory (Butler, 1980), the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village is in the exploration stage. The exploration stage is the stage where a new area begins to develop its area into a tourist destination. The types of attractions are mostly natural and cultural themes that have not been developed seriously. This stage is the initial phase when the local government and society start thinking about developing regional tourism, seeing the potential it has. Judging from the indicators of the TALC exploration stage, the condition of the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village matches the exploration stage.

Even so, based on the results of observations and interviews, it can be seen how the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village has begun to show a phase change, where the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village also has:

- a) Cooperation between the government and local communities is starting to be seen by contributing to the provision of facilities and interaction with tourists for access, although on a limited scale.
- b) Small-scale promotions were started.

The two instruments above are two of several instruments that are in the involvement stage.

Push Factor of Tourism Activities in Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village

This driving factor is the strength and opportunity (strength and opportunity) of tourism activities in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village which will be elaborated through 4 (four) components that must be owned by a tourist attraction, namely: attraction, accessibility, amenity and ancilliary. The description of the four components can be seen below.

1. Attraction

Attractions are the main component that can attract tourists to visit a tourist attraction. There are three types of attractions, namely 1) Natural Resources (natural) where these attractions are in the form of attractions that rely on natural resources owned by a tourist attraction, 2) Cultural tourism attractions, where these attractions are in the form of attractions that rely on the culture of an object. tourism, usually has different characteristics from one tourist attraction to another, and 3) Man-made (man-made) where this attraction is an attraction made by humans themselves.

As the name suggests, Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village offers the main attraction in the form of cultural tourism attractions, which is the strength of the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village, because this means that Sawentar Village has different characteristics from other tourist villages in Blitar Regency or even in Indonesia. The cultural tourism attractions offered are diverse, there are the main icons of Sawentar Village, namely historical-cultural heritage, Sawentar Temple which is well known by the people of Blitar, there are also other tourism activities offered such as traditional sports (Otrah) in the form of Delikan, Enthek, Cublek-Cublek Suweng, Mushroom, Gobak Sodor, Fort. Cultural education in the form of Pranatacara, Javanese Kawi Script, Cucuk Lampah, Batik, Macapat, Craft Arts. And the arts are in the form of Tiban, Jaranan, and Karawitan performances. This attraction is certainly a hallmark of the Blitar community and the local community of Sawentar Village, an experience that only tourists can get when visiting the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village.

2. Accessibility

Accessibility is also the most important thing in a tourism activity. Accessibility can be in the form of all kinds of access to ease of transportation and transportation services that can be taken and used by tourists to be able to visit a tourist attraction. Accessibility can also be in the form of all kinds of access to the convenience of tourists to be able to find and obtain information about a tourist attraction that they want to visit.

Tourists can visit using private vehicles or public transportation such as trains or buses to get to Blitar City, but to get to Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village, until now there is no public transportation that can be used. Air transportation such as airplanes is also not yet available in Blitar, the nearest airport is located in Malang City, which is approximately one and a half hours from Blitar City. From the center of Blitar City itself, it only takes about twenty minutes to get to the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village. To go to Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village, the main road access is considered good and adequate, the roads are smooth without any damage, and of course both two-wheeled and four-wheeled vehicles can be passed—from private four-wheeled vehicles to tourism buses.

3. Amenity (Facilities)

Amenity, amenity, or facilities are all kinds of facilities and infrastructure needed by tourists while in a tourist attraction. The facilities and infrastructure range from accommodation, lodging, restaurants, toilets, transportation, travel agents, and so on.

For now, public facilities owned by Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village are still limited, but adequate. These public facilities include toilets, parking lots, prayer rooms and mosques, and small stalls managed by local people. As for accommodation, the tourist village currently has a homestay that is managed directly by the local community. Although there are only about ten homestays (one of the homestays can be seen in the appendix), these homestays have started operating to accommodate tourists who want to stay at the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village.

4. Ancillary (Additional Service)

Ancillary is an additional service or facility provided by the government from a tourist destination, both for tourists and for tourism actors in related tourist objects. The services provided include marketing, physical development and coordinating all kinds of activities and with all laws and regulations both on roads and in tourist attractions.

The Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village already has a Certificate (SK) for the Cultural Tourism Village given by the DISPARBUDPORA of Blitar Regency in early 2021. The DISPARBUDPORA party is also the party that bridges the management of the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village, POKDARWIS with the Sawentar Village Government and BUMDES. In addition, the DISPARBUDPORA also helps the tourist village to continue to be able to develop knowledge in the field of tourism through various kinds of seminars and training. There is also 1 Puskesmas and 1 Maternity Home in Sawentar Village.

Inhibiting Factors of Tourism Activities in Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village

These inhibiting factors are weaknesses and threats (weaknesses and threats) of tourism activities in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village which will be elaborated through 4 (four) components that must be owned by a tourist attraction, namely: attraction, accessibility, amenities and ancillary. The description of the four components can be seen below.

1. Attraction

There are three types of attractions, namely natural attractions, cultural attractions, and artificial attractions. Of the three types of attractions, Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village has natural attractions in the form of typical rural scenery such as rice fields and rivers, and cultural attractions, which are the main attractions. Culture as the main attraction is certainly a force that can attract tourists with different characteristics from one tourist village destination to other tourist village destinations. However, culture as the main attraction can also be a threat, especially for the authenticity of the culture itself, because with tourism activities, the culture that exists in society can be commodified.

“As for the cultural tourism village in Blitar, Sawentar is indeed the first. But if, for example, the Penataran Temple is turned into a tourist village, yes, it can become the strongest competitor of Sawentar Village. Because from a historical point of view, it is more available there.”

(Interview Results January 25, 2022.)

In the interview, Mr. Nurfi also mentioned how the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village might have competitors in becoming a tourist village, because according to him personally, Penataran Temple has a stronger historical value than Sawentar Village.

2. Accessibility

In addition to accessibility in the form of roads and modes of transportation, access in the form of providing information related to destinations is also important. For now, the weakness of Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village is in providing access to information which is still not optimal. Information about the Cultural Tourism Village in detail and clearly, especially for information about what tourism activities can be done and what facilities and amenities the village has cannot be accessed by tourists. Meanwhile, social media that provides at least information about the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village has not been managed optimally.

3. Amenity (Facilities)

As a tourist destination that is in the exploration stage, Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village already has adequate facilities because tourism activities at Sawentar Temple have existed since 2016. Directions for road signs are also available at several points, as well as a sign that reads "Sawentar Temple". However, for the banner "Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village" there has not been until now. There is also a threat that might arise from the concept of a “family friendly” homestay offered by the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village, especially for millennial tourists, which might reduce their interest in visiting. Because local people tend not to accept tourists of the opposite sex to stay at their homestay.

4. Ancillary (Additional Service)

The Sawentar Village Government and DISPARBUDPORA Blitar Regency have a significant role in seeking additional services in tourism activities in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village. Although according to the results of interviews, seminars and training provided by the DISPARBUDPORA of Blitar Regency are still not diverse and effective in helping participants develop tourism activities, especially in helping the village learn how to do marketing and promotion.

Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village Development Strategy

After identifying the internal and external factors of tourism activities in Sawentar Tourism Village, the IFAS (Internal Factor Analysis Summary) and EFAS (External Factor Analysis Summary) factors can be compiled. These factors will be given a weight and rating with a weight scale (0.00-1.00) and a rating scale (1-4). The assessment can be seen in Table 4.5 Assessment of IFAS (Internal Factor Analysis Summary) in which there are internal factors with indicators in the form of strength (strength) and weakness (weakness) then Table 4.6 Assessment of EFAS (External Factor Analysis Summary) in which there are external factors with indicators in the form of opportunities (opportunity) and threats (threats).

Table 1: Internal Factor Analysis Summary

Internal Factor Strategy	Value	Rate	Score
Strength:			
1. The main attraction is a culture that has its own characteristics.	0,12	4	0,48
2. The icon of Sawentar Temple which is well known to the public.	0,11	4	0,44
3. Adequate accessibility.			
4. Availability of access to information through social media.	0,10	3	0,30
5. Availability of public facilities.	0,09	2	0,18
6. Availability of homestays.	0,10	3	0,30
7. There is an active POKDARWIS.	0,09	3	0,27
	0,07	3	0,21
Weakness:			
1. Marketing is still minimal.	0,11	3	0,33
2. Social media that has not been managed optimally and there is no official website.	0,11	2	0,22
3. The absence of local community human resources who are experts in the field of tourism.	0,10	2	0,20
Total	1		3,35

Source: Researcher, 2022.

Table 2: External Factor Analysis Summary

External Factor Strategy	Value	Rate	Score
Opportunity:			
1. POKDARWIS and local communities who are enthusiastic about tourism activities.	0,13	3	0,39
2. Art that is still preserved by the local community.	0,20	4	0,80
3. Art groups, associations that are still active today.			
4. Village Government and DISPARBUDPORA Blitar Regency which supports tourism activities in Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village.	0,18	4	0,72
	0,17	3	0,51
Threat:			
1. Another tourist village that can be a competitor.	0,10	3	0,30
2. Homestay with a "family friendly" concept	0,10	2	0,20
3. Cultures that may be commodified without realizing it	0,12	3	0,36
Total	1		3,28

Source: Researcher, 2022.

From the two tables above, it can be seen that the IFAS and EFAS factor assessments for each external and internal indicator in tourism activities in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village, where there is a total (final value) that will be mapped into the internal-external matrix quadrant to see the strategic position which can be applied to the development of the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village.

in the strength section, the main attraction in the form of culture that has its own characteristics (weight 0.12 and rating 4), the icon of Candi Sawentar which is well known to the public (weight 0.11 and rating 4) gets the highest weight and rating because it is a two main and important things for the process of developing the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village. Followed by the availability of facilities and amenity, and closed with the existence of POKDARWIS with a weight of 0.09 and a rating of 3. The average rating is dominated by numbers 4 and 3, which means that the strength indicator is already at an adequate rating (outstanding). Only the availability of access to information through social media received a rating of 2 because the existing social media was not yet active and effective in promoting tourism activities as well as sharing information about tourism activities in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village. As for the weakness section, the existing indicators receive a fairly large weight with 0.11 and 0.10 respectively due to lack of marketing, social media that has not been managed optimally and the absence of an official website, the absence of community human resources.

Local experts in the field of tourism have a large enough influence on the development of existing tourism activities, with an average rating of 2 because these indicators still need to be addressed and developed.

the external factor of opportunity (opportunity) has a large average weight and rating. This is because each indicator in external factors is an important opportunity in the development of Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village activities and is currently in adequate condition. Art that is still preserved by the local community. Meanwhile, the external threat factors (threats) get a smaller weight with the consideration that the indicators of these threats are still very manageable with the development strategies that will be formulated.

From the total values that have been obtained in the EFAS and IFAS tables, these values can be converted into nine cells in the IE matrix. The total value obtained in the IFAS table is 3.35 while the EFAS table is 3.28. So if it is converted into nine IE matrix cells, Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village is in quadrant I

Source: Researcher, 2022

Figure 2: Matriks IE Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village.

The Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village above shows the total value of the IE matrix of the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village which is on axis I, which means that tourism activities in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village are described as being in a period of growth and development (grow and build). From the IE matrix above, a SWOT analysis matrix can be drawn up to develop the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village with the strategies undertaken to grow and develop tourism activities in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village.

Table 3: Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village SWOT Matrix

Internal Eksternal	Strength 1. The main attraction is a culture that has its own characteristics. 2. The icon of Sawentar Temple which is well known to the public. 3. Adequate accessibility. 4. Availability of access to information through social media. 5. Availability of public facilities. 6. Availability of homestays. 7. There is an active POKDARWIS.	Weakness 1. Marketing is still minimal. 2. social media that has not been managed optimally and there is no official website.
	Opportunity 1. POKDARWIS and local communities who are enthusiastic about tourism activities. 2. Art that is still preserved by the local community. 3. Art groups, associations that are still	SO Strategy 1. A design for tourism activities in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village is made that prioritizes various cultural activities, where tourists can plunge directly into the daily life of the local community and are guided personally as well as by the local community.

<p>active today.</p> <p>4. Village Government and DISPARBUDPORA Blitar Regency which supports tourism activities in Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village.</p>	<p>2. Cooperate with the government to continue to improve the accessibility and existing facilities in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village.</p> <p>3. The absence of local community human resources who are experts in the field of tourism.</p>	<p>participate in promoting the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village through their respective social media.</p> <p>3. Cooperate with DISPARBUDPORA to participate in promoting social media belonging to the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village.</p>
<p>Threat</p> <p>1. Local communities can help visiting tourists by providing detailed information to overcome the absence of an information center and signposts that are not yet available in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village.</p> <p>2. Inviting local communities to participate in promoting the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village through their respective social media.</p> <p>3. Cooperate with DISPARBUDPORA to participate in promoting social media belonging to the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village.</p>	<p>ST Strategy</p> <p>1. Creating an image or branding of a strong and distinctive cultural tourism village by prioritizing the preservation of the culture owned by the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village.</p> <p>2. Using POKDARWIS as a forum to be able to develop and advance knowledge of local people's human resources regarding tourism activities.</p>	<p>WT Strategy</p> <p>1. Marketing and promotion can be done through website creation, and the creation of interesting content uploaded on social media and other digital platforms such as Youtube or Tik Tok.</p> <p>2. The content is created to show the distinctive culture that exists in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village by involving local communities and associations, existing art groups.</p>

Source: Researcher, 2022.

SWOT Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village above, it can be concluded that the strategies that can be developed in Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village. From this strategy, the strategies that can be developed in accordance with adopting aspects of the tourism village development strategy and community based tourism development strategies are as follows.

1. HR Strengthening Strategy

Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village is a tourist village that is in the exploration stage. In this case, the local community is the first and foremost party who holds the key to tourism activities. So in tourism activities in Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village, it is hoped that the main tourism actors who will contribute are local communities. The strategy for strengthening human resources in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village can then be carried out in the following ways:

- A. Increase local community awareness of Sapta Pesona, namely security, order, cleanliness, coolness, beauty, friendliness, and memories in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village.
- B. Increase local community knowledge of tourism activities by participating in various seminars given by DISPARBUDPORA Blitar Regency or other tourism seminars.
- C. Inviting local communities to participate in supporting tourism activities as a provider of homestays, restaurants, and gift shops or souvenirs.
- D. Invite local communities to join POKDARWIS Sawentar Village.
- E. Continue to preserve youth groups or associations that are engaged in the arts so that the arts in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village will continue to live.

2. Strategy for Making Tour Packages

Tourism planning that can be done to develop tourism activities in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village can be started by making a tour package that is even more interesting than the one that has been made. In its manufacture, the tour package can involve POKDARWIS and representatives from local communities who are not members of POKDARWIS to conduct discussions. Discussions with qualified parties in the tourism sector can also be carried out. Planned tour packages can also be made in more detail, where the tour packages not only offer attractions and tourism activities that tourists can do, but also other facilities that can be obtained such as accommodation and consumption.

3. Marketing Strategy

Marketing is important in developing a tourist destination, where with good marketing, a tourist destination will be increasingly recognized by potential tourists. Good marketing can attract tourists to visit a tourist destination. Marketing that can be done by Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village, among others, is as follows:

A. Ensuring the segment, target, and position of the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village. Namely determining the tourist segment for the tour packages offered, the target of the tour packages offered, and the position of the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village in tourism activities in Blitar Regency.

B. Creating a "quality brand" which is a characteristic and differentiator from other tourist villages. Where the branding of Sawentar Village itself is a tourist village. So in the future, in promoting Sawentar Village, the village must be able to display village branding that matches its name, which is a tourist village that has characteristics and culture that is still alive in society today.

C. Promotional activities, where the media that can be used later, as we are already living in a very fast digital era, can be done through social media or online platforms such as Youtube and Tik Tok. Promotions can be in the form of videos showing various tourism activities that can be carried out in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village. In addition, other activities such as various kinds of events can also be made to attract tourists to visit, especially cultural events. For now, if it is still not possible to create an offline-based event, the village can create an online-based event that can be watched for free using various types of social media platforms ranging from Facebook, Instagram, TikTok or Youtube.

IV. CONCLUSION

1. Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village is a tourism village that is just in the exploration stage, but has begun to show a movement towards the engagement stage. In tourism activities, the driving and inhibiting factors of Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village are as follows:

A. The driving factors for tourism activities in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village are examined from the 4 tourism components, as follows:

1. Has natural attractions and main attractions in the form of a distinctive culture ranging from traditional sports, arts, and cultural education.
2. Access can be reached easily for tourists, either by private two-wheeled or four-wheeled vehicles, or by public transportation. Information can also be accessed through social media Facebook and Instagram.
3. Has fairly complete facilities and has a homestay.
4. Already have a SK from DISPARBUDPORA Blitar Regency, and have POKDARWIS which are running until now.

B. The inhibiting factors for tourism activities in the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village are examined from the 4 components of tourism as follows:

1. The main attraction in the form of culture can make commodification happen.
2. Social media as a place of information that can be accessed by tourists has not been managed effectively and optimally.
3. There is no sign that shows the "Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village" area and the concept of a family-friendly homestay can make millennial tourists reduce their interest in visiting.
4. Activities and training provided by DISPARBUDPORA to help develop tourism activities are still not optimal and not optimal.

2. The strategy for developing the Sawentar Cultural Tourism Village is formulated based on the results of the IE matrix which is in quadrant I and by adopting aspects of the tourism village development strategy, community based tourism development strategy. These strategies include:

A. HR Strengthening Strategy

B. Strategy for Making Tour Packages

C. Marketing Strategy 350 words.

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